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The Impact of Service System Design and Flow Experience on User Satisfaction of the National Health Insurance (JKN) Application: Case Study of Airlangga University Students

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Abstract

This research involves students from Universitas Airlangga to analyze the impact of service system design and flow experience on user satisfaction with the National Health Insurance (JKN) mobile application. The aim of this study is to examine the influence of service system design and flow experience on user satisfaction with the JKN mobile application. This research employs a descriptive quantitative approach, with data collection techniques using questionnaires. The study population consists of Universitas Airlangga students who use the JKN mobile application, with a sample size of 70 respondents. Data analysis was conducted using validity and reliability tests, autocorrelation test (Durbin-Watson test), heteroscedasticity test (Scatterplot), normality test (Kolmogorov-Smirnov test), multiple linear regression analysis, and hypothesis testing. This research is based on two main theories, namely those of Berry et al. (2006), which states that service system design affects user satisfaction in online sites, and DeLone & McLean (2003), which asserts that flow experience also influences user satisfaction in online sites. The analysis results show a positive and significant relationship between service system design and flow experience with user satisfaction of the JKN mobile application, as indicated by the T-test results.

Keywords: *User Satisfaction, Service System Design, Flow Experience, National Health Insurance, Mobile JKN*

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INTRODUCTION

Significant growth has been recorded in the healthcare sector in Indonesia since the introduction of the National Health Insurance (JKN) in 2014. (Efendy et al., 2022).. Despite great progress in healthcare affordability and quality, there are still issues with offline healthcare. Offline health services often face limitations in affordability, quality, and efficiency. This is in the form of limited access to offline health services which results in people having to seek services outside of their area of residence, resulting in higher costs.

The rapid development of technology is accompanied by an increase in the use of electronic communication tools in Indonesia by the public, triggering demands on the government to be more adaptive in providing services to the community. Optimizing public services is intended as a form of strategy in realizing *good governance*. To achieve good governance, government officials need to fulfill various kinds of public services by considering the needs and convenience of the community. One of the government's efforts to expand service coverage by adopting digital technology in institutions, namely the Health Social Security Organizing Agency (BPJS Kesehatan).

In an effort to provide optimal service, BPJS Kesehatan presents the Mobile JKN application. The JKN mobile application is a digital transformation in BPJS Kesehatan's business model, which initially presents administrative activities at branch offices or health facilities, but is now transformed into an application that can be accessed by the public anywhere and anytime without any time restrictions. The utilization of the JKN mobile application brings a number of conveniences to the community, including ease of payment and changing participant data, easy access to understanding information about family participant data, better understanding of participant contribution billing

information, and ease of obtaining information about health facilities and submitting complaints, while fulfilling requests for information related to JKN-KIS. (Prasetyo & Safuan, 2022).

This study seeks to explore the effect of service system design and flow *experience* on user satisfaction of the National Health Insurance (JKN) application. The variables used are similar to the research (Ding et al., 2010) However, the study was aimed at online financial services. While the current author is trying to integrate similar variables, such as service system design with flow experience in health services, namely the JKN Mobile application.

LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Service System Design

In meeting the needs and expectations of more sophisticated users, product service systems have emerged as an industry trend that represents a shift in the strategic focus of manufacturers from selling physical products to providing performance and services (Baines et al., 2007). (Baines et al., 2007). Today's service providers are required to provide the right system design so that the services provided can be efficient, secure, and responsive, thus providing a smooth and satisfying experience for users. (Berry et al., 2006). In their research, they have also proposed three crucial elements in supporting good service system design, such as product variety, service quality, and process features.

- Product Variety

Product variations according to (Norawati et al., 2021) is defined as a product produced by a company and has a variety of different types or designs. Then there is a statement from (Alshurideh, 2016)(Alshurideh, 2016) states that product variety is one of the company's strategies designed to meet user desires and expectations, in responding to users' emotions towards the performance of service providers which can be felt as pleasure or disappointment.

- Service Quality

According to (Goetsch & Davis, 2019) service quality is defined as a dynamic condition involving service products, processes, and environments that can effectively meet the needs or exceed consumer expectations. Service quality is one of the basic factors in helping to run and improve the company's profit business, and is useful in maintaining customer loyalty. (Gobena, 2019).

- Process Features

Process features refer to the extent to which the system offers a fast (or timely) response to requests for information or action (Nelson et al., 2014). (Nelson et al., 2014). Furthermore, process features in online sites involve the use of process intelligence to monitor, analyze, and optimize user interactions according to (Akhavan & Hassannayebi, 2024).

2. Flow Experience

In 1975, psychologist Csikszentmihalyi proposed a theory of flow that explores the internal psychological state of an individual that results when a person engages in certain behaviors or activities. A person who is in a flow experience is in a state of awareness with strong concentration, so there is no time to think about anything else. Thus, according to the theory of (Csikszentmihalyi et al., 1990)(Csikszentmihalyi et al., 1990), individuals who feel flow from a certain experience tend to continue the activity. However, when the individual is not in flow, they will feel irritated or bored, even trying to escape from the experience at hand.

Flow experience according to (Bagozzi & Dholakia, 1999)(Bagozzi & Dholakia, 1999), can encourage a person to have cognitive and emotional tendencies while browsing the internet. This is in line with (Novak et al., 2000)(Novak et al., 2000), that the flow experience emerges as a key variable for understanding user behavior in digital outlets, so that a good and pleasant user experience will lead to high levels of satisfaction and engagement. (See-To et al., 2012).. Furthermore, (Hoffman et al., 1996) (Hoffman et al., 1996) suggested that online flow as a cognitive state experienced by customers during navigation, jointly determined by skill and control, high levels of challenge, focused attention, and enhanced by interactivity.

- Control

User-perceived control is based on the premise that individuals should be able to recognize control in their environment. Giving people the choice to make decisions is a traditional method of introducing control (Zheng et al., 2020). (Zheng et al., 2020). People who have

high perceived control perceive themselves as further away from negative targets and closer to positive targets (Han, 2018). (Han, 2018). Thus, control behaviors can encourage people to distance themselves further from bad things which will increase their sense of well-being and achieve overall satisfaction. (Wang et al., 2021).

- Skills

Skills in the digital sphere relate to abilities related to computer literacy, specifically the capacity to use technology by those who have access to it (Morte-Nadal & Esteban-Navarro, 2022). (Morte-Nadal & Esteban-Navarro, 2022).. In research that has been conducted by (Hahnel et al., 2016)(Hahnel et al., 2016), users who have skills in websites tend to be more effective in monitoring the information they read, often decide to search for relevant information again, and have a higher probability of completing tasks correctly compared to less skilled users.

- Focused Attention

To stay in the flow experience, users must concentrate on the activity they are doing. A website is key to a company's success, as it acts as a communication tool between the company and the customer (Qalati et al., 2021). When users are accessing a website, they sometimes have constraints caused by limited resources of time and information processing. While accessing websites, users often get a lot of distractions caused by website conditions or other online activities such as instant messages, emails, or advertisements from other websites. Such distractions will limit the focus of the user's attention while accessing the web.

- Interactivity

In (L. Wu, 2019) interactivity is defined as a key characteristic including user control over what information will be presented, how long it will be presented, and what information will follow. In line with this, (Arghashi & Yuksel, 2022) revealed that interactivity has an influence on user satisfaction. Interactivity gives users greater control over online information which can increase their perception of control thereby compensating for feelings of reduced control that may be present while using the product.

- Challenge

According to research on flow experience conducted by (Özhan & Kocadere, 2020)(Özhan & Kocadere, 2020), the perceived challenge of an activity allows individuals to feel engaged. Challenge on the other hand, determines how much the user feels compelled to act on the app. This is proven through research conducted by (I. L. Wu et al., 2020)(I. L. Wu et al., 2020), the challenge of finding a service that matches the user's desires will trigger a positive emotional response which then creates a user flow experience. When the application fails to provide adequate challenges, users tend to feel bored and less interested in exploring the application further, and vice versa.

3. User Satisfaction

Satisfaction on online sites according to (Harrati et al., 2016) is attributed to when users feel confident that the system meets their needs. Related to that, (Berry et al., 2006) suggests that product variety can attract new customers and retain existing customers by offering a broad range of products, detailed information, and powerful analytical tools. Important elements in service system design, such as product variety, service quality, and process features, can create a good flow experience, which in turn increases user satisfaction and shapes behavior that will ensure sustainable competitive advantage in the future. (Chase & Dasu, 2001).

4. National Health Insurance Application

Mobile Jaminan Kesehatan Nasional Badan Penyelenggara Jaminan Sosial Kesehatan (Mobile JKN BPJS) is a mobile application created and developed by BPJS Kesehatan Indonesia. The Mobile JKN application was created to answer the challenges of digital transformation of the BPJS Kesehatan service model. (et al., 2022). Administrative services can now be done through this application, making it easier for users, because it can be done anywhere and anytime. Based on data (Social Security Organizing Agency, 2024) the number of JKN mobile users in January 2024 was 267.7 million, up from 241.7 million in June 2022. The increase in users is in line with the increasingly complete features provided by the Mobile-JKN application, such as premium features, payment features, service history features, complaint features, and several others.

METHOD

This type of research is descriptive quantitative with data collection techniques through questionnaires. The descriptive approach aims to describe and determine the effect of Service System Design, and flow experience on JKN mobile application user satisfaction at Universitas Airlangga. Meanwhile, the quantitative approach is rooted in a natural setting of systematic wholeness and develops and uses mathematical models. Quantitative data analysis is carried out to obtain all the necessary data.

The type of data used is subject data from primary data sources obtained through distributing questionnaires. The population in this study were Universitas Airlangga students who used the JKN Mobile application, with a sample size of 70 respondents. This study uses multiple linear regression data analysis techniques and parametric hypothesis testing statistical tests to determine how much the contribution of service system design variables and flow experience to user satisfaction simultaneously and to evaluate the regression coefficient of the study.

The data obtained from the tests were processed and analyzed using Statistical Product and Service Solutions (SPSS). Data analysis includes various stages. These include reliability test, validity, normality test (Kolmogorov-Smirnov), heteroscedasticity test (Scatterplot), autocorrelation test (Durbin-Watson test), multiple linear regression test, and hypothesis testing. These stages ensure systematic data processing and analysis produce valid results.

RESEARCH

Validity Test Result

Table 1. X₁ Validity Test Results

Statement	Pearson Correlation	Sig,	R Table	Description
X1.1	0,680	<001	0,235	Valid
X1.2	0,689	<001	0,235	Valid
X1.3	0,667	<001	0,235	Valid
X1.4	0,689	<001	0,235	Valid
X1.5	0,578	<001	0,235	Valid
X1.6	0,622	<001	0,235	Valid
X1.7	0,724	<001	0,235	Valid
X1.8	0,694	<001	0,235	Valid
X1.9	0,680	<001	0,235	Valid

Source: Results of Processed SPSS Data

Based on the validity test carried out in table X.1, it can be ascertained that the System Design Variable has a Valid statement for all statement items with a calculated r value greater than r table, namely 0.235. All of the X.1 Variables above can be confirmed to have valid information for all item statements.

Table 2. X₂ Variable Validity Test Results

Statement	Pearson Correlation	Sig,	R Table	Description
X2.1	0,680	<001	0,235	Valid
X2.2	0,600	<001	0,235	Valid
X2.3	0,648	<001	0,235	Valid
X2.4	0,700	<001	0,235	Valid
X2.5	0,476	<001	0,235	Valid
X2.6	0,523	<001	0,235	Valid
X2.7	0,610	<001	0,235	Valid
X2.8	0,728	<001	0,235	Valid
X2.9	0,659	<001	0,235	Valid
X2.10	0,687	<001	0,235	Valid
X2.11	0,613	<001	0,235	Valid
X2.12	0,418	<001	0,235	Valid
X2.13	0,603	<001	0,235	Valid

X2.14	0,551	<001	0,235	Valid
X2.15	0,576	<001	0,235	Valid

Source: Results of Processed SPSS Data

Based on the validity test carried out in table X.2, it can be ascertained that the flow experience variable has a valid statement for all statement items with a calculated r value greater than r table, namely 0.235. The entire X.2 variable above can be confirmed to have a valid statement for all item statements.

Table 3. Y Variable Validity Test Results

Statement	Pearson Correlation	Sig,	R Table	Description
Y.1	0,235	<.001	0,868	Valid
Y.2	0,235	<.001	0,862	Valid
Y.3	0,235	<.001	0,805	Valid

Source: Results of Processed SPSS Data

Based on the results of the Validity test carried out on Variable Y1, it can be ascertained that the User Satisfaction Variable test has a valid statement for all statement items with a calculated r value greater than r table, namely 0.235. Therefore, it can be concluded that the question items for each variable (service system design, flow experience, user satisfaction) are declared valid because all questions produce a value of $R_{hitung} > R_{tabel}$.

Reliability Test Results

Reliability testing uses Cronbach's Alpha to determine whether the 27 variables (questions) are reliable. The reliability requirement is that the Cronbach's Alpha value must be greater than the rtable value. To determine the rtable value, the formula n (number of variables) - 2 is used, namely $70 - 2 = 68$. With a significance level of 5% (0.05), the rtable value is 0.198.

Table 4. Reliability Test Results

Variables	Cronbach's Alpha	Description
System Design	0,841	Reliable
Flow Experience	0,872	Reliable
Satisfaction	0,800	Reliable

Source: Results of Processed SPSS Data

An alpha value > 0.7 indicates that the reliability of the instrument is adequate, while an alpha value > 0.80 indicates that all items in the test are consistent and have strong reliability. Alternatively, the interpretation of alpha values is as follows: If alpha > 0.90 , reliability is considered very high. An alpha value between 0.70 to 0.90 indicates high reliability. If alpha is in the range of 0.50 to 0.70, reliability is considered moderate. However, if alpha < 0.50 , reliability is considered low. Low reliability may be due to the inconsistency of one or more items.

From the results of the Reliability test above, it is known that the test of variable X.1 System Design shows 0.841 and X.2 flow experience shows 0.872 and Variable Y1 User Satisfaction shows 0.800. Based on these tests, it can be concluded that these variables have reliable information.

Residual Normality Test

The residual normality test ensures that the residuals of the regression model are normally distributed. This is important for the validity of statistical inference in linear regression, as residual normality ensures accurate parameter estimation and the validity of the hypothesis tests performed.

Figure 1. Residual Normality Test Results (Source: Results of Processed SPSS Data)

Based on the results of testing the normality of residuals using the graphical method on the Normal P-P Plot of Regression Standardized Residual graph, it can be seen that the data is spread around the diagonal line and follows a pattern that matches the diagonal line. This indicates that the data is normally distributed.

Heteroscedasticity Test

The heteroscedasticity test is conducted to identify the presence of non-constant variability in the residuals of the regression model. This test ensures that the variance of the residuals is constant for all predictor values (homoscedasticity). Heteroscedasticity may indicate an invalid regression model, as inaccurate standard error estimates may affect significance tests.

Heteroscedasticity Test Results (Source: Results of Processed SPSS Data)

Based on the results of heteroscedasticity testing using scatterplot, it can be seen that there is no clear wavy, widening, or narrowing pattern. The data points are scattered around the number 0 on the Y axis, both above and below it. From this test, it can be concluded that there is no heteroscedasticity in the regression model, which means that the regression model does not experience interference.

Regression Test

Regression test to determine the linear relationship between the dependent variable and one or more independent variables. This test aims to measure the effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable, as well as make predictions of the value of the dependent variable based on the value of the independent variable.

Table 5. Regression Test Results

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	3.085	1.313		2.35	0.022

System Design	0.153	0.053	0.409	2.908	0.005
Flow Experience	0.074	0.033	0.315	2.239	0.029

Source: Results of Processed SPSS Data

From the results of Regression testing carried out in the table, it shows that the constant value is positive. This means that the value of variable X is considered not constant or not equal to zero, then the system design and flow experience have an effect on satisfaction. The variable coefficient X.1 System Design is 0.153 and X.2 flow experience is 0.074 which has a positive status that the effect of System Design and flow experience on Satisfaction is positive and quite strong.

Multiple Linear Regression Test

The author chooses multiple linear regression test analysis to be able to determine how much influence the independent variables, namely: service system design (X1) and flow experience (X2) on the dependent variable user satisfaction (Y). According to (Sherly & Isharijadi, 2013: 6) the multiple linear regression equation can be formulated with:

Table 6. Multiple Linear Test Results

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	3.085	1.313		2.35	0.022
System Design	0.153	0.053	0.409	2.908	0.005
Flow Experience	0.074	0.033	0.315	2.239	0.029

Source: Results of Processed SPSS Data

Based on the output of the spss test results, the results of the multiple linear regression equation in this study are:

$$Y = 3.085 + 0.153X_1 + 0.074X_2$$

Description:

1. Constant Value = 3.085, a positive constant value indicates a positive influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable in one unit. The increase in the independent variable (Service System Design and flow experience) will lead to an increase in the dependent variable (User Satisfaction).
2. The coefficient value on the Service System Design variable is positive, which is 0.153, meaning that if the Service System Design increases, then User Satisfaction will increase by 0.153 units assuming other independent variables remain.

The coefficient value on the flow experience variable is positive, which is 0.074, meaning that if the flow experience increases, then User Satisfaction will increase by 0.074 units, assuming other independent variables remain.

Multiple Correlation Analysis (R)

The autocorrelation test is applied to detect whether the residuals of the regression model are related to each other or not. Autocorrelation can indicate the presence of patterns in the residuals that are not captured by the model, which is especially important in time series data.

Table 7. Multiple Correlation Analysis Results

Information	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Conclusion
Multiple Linear Regression	0.682	0.465	0.449	Strong

Source: Results of Processed SPSS Data

Based on the results of the R test above, the R value shows R = 0.682 which indicates that the independent variables have a strong influence on the dependent variable, namely User Satisfaction.

Determinant Coefficient Analysis (R)²

The Model Summary output table shows that the Adjusted R Square value is 0.465 or 46.5%. This value indicates that the service system design and flow experience variables affect user satisfaction by 46.5%, while the other 53.5% is influenced by other variables not included in this study. The magnitude of the Standard Error of the Estimate in this study is 1.152, which means that the error in predicting user satisfaction is 1.152.

Then to find out whether the hypothesis proposed in this study is accepted or rejected, the authors conducted the T test and F test with the following results:

Partial Significance Test (T Test)

In this study, we conducted the T test to determine how much influence each independent variable has on the dependent variable individually. Before conducting the T test, it is necessary to calculate the t table value, the resulting t table value for this study is $t(\alpha/2; n-k-1) = t(0.025; 70-2-1) = t(0.025; 67) = 1.996$

Table 8. Significant Test Results of Partial Effect

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)	3.085	1.313		2.350	.022		
System Design	.153	.053	.409	2.908	.005	.404	2.474
Flow Experience	.074	.033	.315	2.239	.029	.404	2.274

Source: Results of Processed SPSS Data

Through the table, it is known:

1. System design (X1) has a significance value of 0.005, $0.005 < 0.05$ and a calculated t value of $2.908 > t$ table 1.996. This means that system design (X1) has an effect on user satisfaction (Y).
2. Flow experience (X2) has a significance value of 0.029, $0.029 < 0.05$ and a calculated t value of $2.239 > t$ table 1.996. This means that flow experience (X2) has an effect on user satisfaction (Y).

Simultaneous Significance Test (F Test)

The author uses the F test to determine the level of significance of the influence of the independent variables (X) together or simultaneously on the dependent variable (Y). Before conducting the F test to determine whether the independent variables (X) together have an effect or not on the dependent variable (Y), it is necessary to determine the value of the F table first, namely with $\alpha = 5\%$ and degrees of freedom (df) = n-k (n is the number of samples and k is the number of independent variables). F table = f (k: n-k) = f (2 :68) = 3.132

Table 9. Simultaneous Significant Test Results (F Test)

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	77.149	2	38.574	29.088	.000 ^b
Residuals	88.851	67	1.326		
Total	166	69			

Source: Results of Processed SPSS Data

In the test results above, it is known that the significance value for the effect of service system design and flow experience simultaneously on user satisfaction is $0.000 < 0.05$ and the calculated F value is $29.088 > 3.132$, from these results new findings are obtained that the service system design and flow experience simultaneously have a significant impact on user satisfaction. Furthermore, the effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable can be seen in the following figure:

Figure 3. Partial Significant Test Results (Source: Results of Processed SPSS Data)

DISCUSSION

1. The effect of service system design on user satisfaction of the Mobile-JKN application

The results of the research above show that X1 has a positive and significant effect on Y. It can be said that the service system design in the Mobile-JKN application which includes service quality, product variety, and process features has a significant impact on creating user satisfaction with the Mobile-JKN application. With a good service system design, users can get the desired service without obstacles, which in turn will increase user satisfaction with the application. Therefore, service system design is one of the dominant factors in increasing user satisfaction with the Mobile-JKN application. The results of this study are in line with research conducted by (Berry et al., 2006) which states that service system design affects user satisfaction on online sites.

2. The effect of flow experience on user satisfaction of the Mobile-JKN application

Based on the results of the study, it shows that X2 has a positive and significant effect on Y. This shows that the Mobile-JKN application is able to present the user's flow experience including the fulfillment of the factors of challenge, skill, control, focused attention, and interactivity. Applications that are able to create a user flow experience will have a significant impact on increasing user satisfaction. Users who can experience flow tend to feel more satisfied because they feel involved in the features provided through the design of the service system, so they are in a state of awareness with strong concentration without thinking about anything else outside the application. Therefore, the flow experience is one of the dominant factors in increasing user satisfaction with the Mobile-JKN application, which is also in line with research by (See-To et al., 2014). (See-To et al., 2012)(See-To et al., 2012), that flow experience affects user satisfaction in online sites.

Finding Research

In accordance with the results of the F test described in the results and discussion section, it can be concluded that X1 and X2 together or simultaneously have a significant effect on Y. Through the results of this study, new findings are obtained which show that service system design and flow experience significantly affect user satisfaction with the Mobile-JKN application. This finding provides valuable insight into the importance of these two factors in increasing user satisfaction with the Mobile-JKN application. By integrating effective service system design and creating a positive flow experience, the Mobile-JKN application can provide an optimal positive user experience, and ultimately lead to increased user satisfaction. This research proves that a holistic approach that considers both factors is needed, in order to create an application that is able to meet user needs and expectations

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the study, it can be concluded that service system design and flow experience have a significant impact on user satisfaction of the National Health Insurance (JKN) application among Universitas Airlangga students. Good service system design and pleasant flow experience when using the JKN application are the main factors in increasing user satisfaction. Therefore, it is recommended that JKN application managers consistently improve the quality of service system design and pay attention to flow experience aspects to provide a more optimal

experience for users, so that user satisfaction can be continuously improved. In addition, more intensive socialization is needed regarding the usefulness and benefits of the JKN application so that people, especially students, can take full advantage of this application.

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